

Geological mapping of Arsinoes and Pyrrhae Chaos E. Luzzi¹, A. P. Rossi¹

¹Jacobs University Bremen

Chaotic terrains such as Arsinoes and Pyrrhae Chaos are wide areas characterized by a basaltic bedrock affected by kilometric faults and fractures that cause a polygonal pattern of blocks and knobs. The bedrock within the Chaotic terrains is identified in literature as the Chaotic terrain unit ([1],[2]) and it is subdivided into three subunits: Fractured plain, Knobby terrain and High Thermal Inertia Chaotic terrain [3]. The Fractured plain subunit represents the less eroded subunit of the Chaotic terrain: it is still possible to observe the mesas separated by the deep faults. The Knobby terrain subunit shows the same spectral signature of the Fractured plain and is always in lateral contact with it, that's why it is reasonable to consider the Knobby terrain as the erosional evolution of the Fractured plain. The High Thermal Inertia Chaotic terrain occurs in Arsinoes Chaos only in a small area in the northeastern part of the Chaos and shows heavy erosion and higher thermal inertia than the other two subunits. In the central part of Arsinoes Chaos, stratigraphically above the Knobby terrain, a light-toned layered unit lies with a dip direction of 100-130 and a dip angle between 4° and 26°. The layered unit has been interpreted as a sedimentary unit, rich in phyllosilicates (perhaps associated with sulfates). The hematite, occurring abundantly in the nearby Aram Chaos [3] was not detected in significant amount. The last unit lies unconformably on top of the sedimentary unit and thus it was informally called Cap unit, with no references to the Cap unit described by [3], since the CRISM cube does not show sulfates in this plateau-like unit in Arsinoes Chaos and also the scalloped morphology is less pronounced than in Aram. In Pyrrhae Chaos the succession is limited to the Fractured plain and the Knobby terrain, posing an unresolved question about the differences between the two terrains that may have caused the lack of sedimentary units in Pyrrhae Chaos. A dense network of grabens and pit chains, likely of volcanic origin, was also mapped and will be further investigated through fractal analyses and analog experiments.

References: [1] Carr, M. H., Masursky, H., & Saunders, R. S. (1973). *JGR*, 78(20), 4031-4036 [2] Sharp, R. P. et al. (1971). *JGR*, 76(2), 331-342. [3] Glotch, T. D., & Christensen, P. R. (2005) *JGR-Planets*, 110(E9).